

CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART VI. COMPOUNDS OF BERYLLIUM
CHLORIDE WITH UREA, BENZAMIDE, THIOUREA AND
SUBSTITUTED THIOUREAS

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The formation of the complex compounds of beryllium chloride with urea, benzamide, thiourea, phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl-, diphenyl- and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-ditolyl-thioureas in organic solvents has been studied and their structures have been discussed.

A survey of literature shows that no work has been done on the formation of complex compounds of beryllium chloride with urea, amides and thioureas. The present work was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of beryllium chloride with urea, benzamide, thiourea and symmetrical as well as unsymmetrical thioureas.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous beryllium chloride was prepared, as reported in an earlier paper (*this Journal*, 1957, 34, 317).

An alcoholic solution of urea or benzamide was taken in a well-corked conical flask and an ethereal solution of BeCl_2 added slowly with constant stirring. The mixture was shaken well for sometime, excess of the solvent distilled off and the mother-liquor allowed to crystallise in vacuum. With urea, the complex compound separated out first, which was recrystallised from absolute alcohol, but in the case of benzamide, it crystallised out first and then the complex compound separated out at a low temperature in white square plates from the mother-liquor.

Similar procedure was followed in the preparation of thiourea and substituted thiourea complexes. In each of the cases, when the mixture was cooled the unchanged thiourea crystallised out first. The complex compound separated out from the mother-liquor after keeping it for several days in a vacuum desiccator.

Complex compounds of beryllium chloride with urea and benzamide were also prepared in ether medium by adding a known weight of urea or benzamide to the excess of BeCl_2 in ether and then shaking the mixture for several hours. After the reaction was over, the supernatant liquid was decanted off and the compounds obtained were washed several times with dry ether. These were first dried between the folds of filter paper and finally in vacuum.

When the same procedure was followed, thiourea and substituted thioureas formed no compounds.

Beryllium, chlorine and nitrogen were estimated by using the same methods as described in Part II (*loc. cit.*). Sulphur was estimated by the fusion method.

General Properties.—Urea and benzamide complexes are white in colour, not hygroscopic and melt at $213-14^\circ$ and $107-109^\circ$ respectively. The complex compounds

obtained with thiourea and substituted thioureas are all coloured, very hygroscopic and decompose readily in air. These are insoluble in common organic solvents but are soluble in alcohol.

TABLE I

Amides and thioureas.	% Be.		% Cl.		% Nitrogen.		Colour.	Compound.
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		
1. Urea	2.91	2.81	22.20	22.19	34.81	35.00	White	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
2. Benzamide	2.80	2.79	22.01	22.05	8.62	8.66	Do	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
					% Sulphur.			
3. Thiourea	3.80	3.88	30.17	30.60	27.64	27.58	Yellow	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
4. Phenyl-T*	3.83	3.88	30.17	30.60	13.72	13.71	Light yellow	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
5. <i>o</i> -Tolyl-T	3.61	3.66	28.80	28.85	12.94	13.01	Light pink	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot o\text{-Tol} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
6. <i>m</i> -Tolyl-T	3.60	3.66	28.80	28.86	12.94	13.01	Do	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot m\text{-Tol} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
7. <i>p</i> -Tolyl-T	3.64	3.66	28.82	28.86	12.97	13.01	Do	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot p\text{-Tol} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
8. Diphenyl-T	2.90	2.92	23.02	23.05	10.34	10.39	Light yellow	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot \text{Ph} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{Ph}$
9. <i>o</i> -Ditolyl-T	2.62	2.68	21.04	21.13	9.47	9.52	Pink	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3$
10. <i>m</i> -Ditolyl-T	2.64	2.68	21.04	21.13	9.50	9.52	Do	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot m\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3$
11. <i>p</i> -Ditolyl-T	2.64	2.68	21.06	21.13	9.48	9.52	Do	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3$

*T denotes thiourea

DISCUSSION

Beryllium chloride forms a crystalline stable complex in which four molecules of urea combine with one molecule of beryllium chloride. The carbonyl group present in the urea molecule being very reactive and also the affinity of beryllium towards oxygen being strong, it appears that chlorine is readily displaced to the outer ring, as has been observed by Ephraim and Biltz (*Ber.*, 1912, 46, 1323, 1330; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 81, 532; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 148, 157; 1927, 166, 341) in the case of ammonia and by Fricke and Havestadt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 146, 121; 1926, 182, 357) in the case of methylamine and ethylenediamine. The compound may be represented as:

It is interesting to note that only two molecules of benzamide combine with one molecule of BeCl_2 . It appears that the aromatic group present in the benzamide molecule offers steric hindrance and the carbonyl group becomes sufficiently weak to displace chlorine to the outer ring. The octet of the beryllium is completed by two

co-ordinate links from -CO- group in which oxygen acts as the donor and the two covalent links of the chlorine. The compound can be represented as :

The result is similar to our previous work on compounds of amines with beryllium chloride (*loc. cit.*) and also of other workers (Fricke *et al.*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 146, 103, 121; 1926, 152, 347, 357; 1927, 163, 31; 1928, 170, 125) who observe that the aromatic amines form only diamines and only two molecules of benzaldehyde combine with one molecule of BeCl_2 (Fricke and Havestadt, *loc. cit.*).

Thiocarbamide readily forms complex compounds with different metallic salts (Maly, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 172; Rosenheim and Meyer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 49, 13; Mussgnug and Vanino, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 21; Haworth and Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 661) in which one, two or three molecules of thiourea combine with one molecule of the metallic salt. In these complex compounds sulphur atom present as thiocarbonyl group acts as the donor, forming stable complexes.

Thiourea forms the complex compound $\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_2\text{CSNH}_2$ with beryllium chloride in ether-alcohol mixture, but not in water or in a slightly acidic solution. It is similar to the complex compounds of ZnCl_2 , CdCl_2 and HgCl_2 (Maly, *loc. cit.*; Rosenheim and Meyer, *loc. cit.*) in many respects, but differs from them in being hygroscopic and readily hydrolysable.

Though both nitrogen and sulphur are present in the molecule yet co-ordination through sulphur has been suggested in all these cases (vide references cited above). Morgan and Burstall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 143) suggest that the thiourea complexes, in which sulphur of the thiocarbonyl and nitrogen of the amino group co-ordinate, are highly complex in nature and usually the compounds contain more than one metal atoms combined with several molecules of the thiocarbamide. Sahasrabudhey and Krall (*this Journal*, 1942, 19, 25; 1944, 21, 63) observed that the formation of complex compounds between cupric sulphate and phenylthiocarbamide was largely influenced by temperature and suggested that the co-ordination occurred exclusively through sulphur atom. Even in its reaction with nitrous acid (Sahasrabudhey and Krall, *loc. cit.*), $-\text{NH}_2$ group present in phenylthiocarbamide is not attacked but oxidation occurs and the nitro derivative of Hector's base is formed. It seems probable that the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups in thiourea are not 'amino' in the conventional sense, as is evident from the fact that salts of the type of amine hydrochloride are not known. Further, the complex compound, $\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{CS}$, is very hygroscopic, which goes to prove beyond doubt that the co-ordination is not through nitrogen as the amino complexes are sufficiently stable. From these considerations it appears that the co-ordination is through sulphur, and the compound may be represented as :

It is surprising that only one molecule each of unsymmetrical and symmetrical thioureas combines with one molecule of beryllium chloride. Beryllium chloride molecule is supposed to be sp^3 hybridised (Cartmell and Fowles, "Valency and Molecular Structure", p. 147). On the approach of a pair of electrons, the mode of hybridisation changes to the sp^2 state. Out of the two vacant orbitals, one is filled up by a lone pair of electrons from the sulphur atom (perhaps the second molecule of the thioureas does not take part in co-ordination due to steric reasons). As the beryllium atom readily assumes the maximum covalency of four, it seems probable that one of the chlorine atoms donates a lone pair of electrons (for filling up the second vacant orbital) as back co-ordination rather than the second pair being derived from the same sulphur atom. Similarly, Goremykin and Gladyshevskaya (*J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1942, **13**, 762; 1944, **14**, 13) suggested polynuclear structures involving hydrazine bridges in preference to chelate structures in the case of $\text{P}(\text{Cl})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)$ and $\text{PdBr}_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)$. Thus, the compounds may be represented in the case of unsymmetrical thioureas as

and in the case of symmetrical thioureas as :

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to Dr. S. S. Joshi, D.Sc., Head of the Department of Chemistry, for providing necessary facilities.